

Moral Courage Motivation During Social Movements

Sreenidhi Jadda

The past has seen many instances of people who, despite facing great challenges and having to make sacrifices, remained determined in their pursuit of justice. The voluntary risks taken by the heroes who advocate for a better future cannot be fathomed by those who simply do not believe their actions can have an impact because they are driven by a personal purpose to change the world. A question arises when acknowledging the reasons behind this sense of purpose: What motivates the desire for justice to outweigh associated compromises and help individuals pursue a goal in the context of having moral courage during social movements? In the stimulus packet, courage was the most prominent theme that inspired this question because throughout the sources it was evident that courage, whether in the context of vulnerability or bravery, helped many people take chances that led them to make new progress. Some argue the choice to participate in social movements emerges from individualism or societal pressure, while others believe a sense of community and purpose is what motivates individuals to have a desire for justice. Moral courage, when applied has a high potential to reward long-term societal changes. When individuals stand up for their beliefs, they can help shift the balance of power, encouraging others and creating positive changes for the future of their communities. The desire to improve the future of one's community motivates people to learn how to make compromises and collaborate with others inspiring moral courage in social movements.

Individuals become motivated to advocate for a cause by working with one another and taking advantage of collective resources and opinions to achieve a common goal because it

makes the process easier and results more effective. Dr. Grant M. Gutierrez, who received a Ph.D. from Dartmouth College in Political Ecology explores environmental justice through social movements. He explained that the force of vulnerability is a process of “self-determination and an acute sense of community that emerge from shared experiences of the resistance to and confrontation of the structural violence of... living with the category of ‘the vulnerability slot’” (Gutierrez et al., 2021). Vulnerability in this context creates resilience within social movements, especially for marginalized groups. When people facing similar challenges come together, they find comfort in shared experiences and inspiration from each other's strengths and perspectives. By using vulnerability to bring people together, these groups make their many voices heard, allowing them to challenge powerful authority. Individuals in society depend on each other as one person's actions and choices can ultimately influence power dynamics when facing opposition. An article published in 2023 by the RSnake Show, which focuses on social and societal issues, explores the most effective solutions for overcoming obstacles during a social movement. The most profound solutions are: “[f]orming partnerships with other organizations or groups that share similar goals can strengthen the movement by pooling resources, expertise, and influence,” as well as “[d]eveloping strong relationships among movement participants can foster unity and facilitate cooperation, even when differences in opinions or priorities arise” (Hansen 2023). As explained in the other sources, a sense of community is a powerful weapon against the many compromises and obstacles that might be faced during a social movement. This creates trust and support among groups of people, allowing them to work together to make achieving their shared goals easier, rather than individually attempting to solve difficult problems. Gilda Zwerman, a professor in the Sociology department at SUNY Old Westbury explores the success

of morally “good” and “bad” social movements. Thoughtful responses to repression while encountering opposition such as police are crucial as protestors must avoid arrest and violence to ensure the success of a movement. While it may seem sensible to retreat in the face of repression in the short term to avoid further harm, “dispersing a disruptive action can often guarantee failure, because the movement may not have the capacity to rebuild its strength and recapture the leverage” (Zwerman et al., 2021). Without the resilience gained from a unified movement, the effectiveness and success of the social movement are compromised. Regardless, some people may be hesitant to collaborate with others because they want to avoid possible disagreements and differences in beliefs. They could be more motivated by individualism and take action for themselves because they may feel that working in a group diminishes their personal contributions or won’t benefit them at all in the moment. Researcher Ge-Qi Cui explains “In an individualist society, individuals care only or primarily for themselves and their immediate families, whereas in a collectivist culture, individuals enjoy membership in a group that rewards loyalty. However, studies suggest that, at the individual level, individualism and collectivism represent separate cultural dimensions because both can exist within the same culture” (Cui et al., 2022). If a society places a high value on individualism, individuals may be more likely to prioritize their own interests over those of their community. But those who are truly willing to give it their all and have the most courage during social movements are the ones who have the most challenging environment to work in and the greatest need to overcome and deal with those compromises. So whether it is for individualistic reasons or for one’s community, being a part of a social movement can still make an impact as long as the appropriate efforts are made.

A genuine desire to make a difference is a major motivator for advocating for a cause. Being willing to stand up to authority or confront challenges directly requires courage and determination which comes from having a strong enough sense of purpose to overcome adversity. While it is a significant support, people cannot solely rely on others for backup and resources to be a part of a successful social movement. Pauline Armsby, a personal and professional development learning coach, lecturer, and researcher conducted a study to explore Filipino physical therapists' views on social responsibility. According to the participants, “[i]t is usually motivated by one's personal values and goes beyond one's interest. As participant Jose said, “It's like doing everything in your power to help alleviate whatever problem... to improve the conditions of the society” (Palad et al., 2024). This commitment to social responsibility highlights the potential of individuals and their ability to affect societal progress. For social movements to be successful, they “cannot be ‘greedy.’ They must... prepare participants for the dangers and risks of each protest, and allow each individual to choose—without coercion—which actions they are willing to take” (Zwerman et al., 2021). Social movements can ensure their unity and protect the well-being and freedom of participants by adhering to these values. A participant must understand the associated compromises to help prevent internal conflicts and help the movement become stronger. Bernard Stringer, a member of the Central Committee of the Black Student Union and a leader of the San Francisco State Strike, explains that firsthand exposure to social injustices from participants' backgrounds in working-class communities motivated them to fight for change. During a campus rally, “Four-hundred and thirty-five [students] were arrested in the “mass bust” and “[t]he arrests added new responsibilities for bail, lawyers, and court dates” (Epstein et al., 2022). Surprisingly, the

increase in setbacks made participants more determined, demonstrating their courage in the face of adversity and commitment to the cause. “The Black students had initiated the struggle because the situation of Black people was so horrible in regard to educational equity” (Epstein et al., 2022). They recognized that their efforts were not just about improving their own circumstances but were also about creating more opportunities for their communities in the future. Jacob Lawrence is an artist who mainly focuses on the human condition, American history, and themes of social justice. His artwork, *Confrontation on the Bridge* depicts the African American non-violent protests for voting rights during the 1965 Selma to Montgomery marches. The protestors are confronted by the vicious dog on the left at the end of the Edmund Pettus Bridge. This dog represents the power imbalance of armed police troops versus unarmed protestors. The artwork focuses on the protestors with fearful expressions, but they still chose to risk their lives, seeking a better future for African Americans. It takes a lot of moral courage to continue to fight for justice when an individual is putting themselves in danger to put their community first. Melinda Janko, the author of a biography about Elouise Cobell personally knew her and explained her inspiring journey. Cobell was fed up with the government's lies and injustices due to their negligence in providing basic survival resources to Blackfeet Indians, so she started taking proactive approaches to bring justice. The government never took her seriously, but she didn't give up and filed “the largest class-action lawsuit... against the U.S. government” (Janko 2013). Eventually, after 15 long years of hard work, she and her lawyers agreed to a \$3.4 billion settlement. Cobell proved that a sense of justice is enough motivation to take on the challenging journey of fighting for what one believes in. She was determined to bring attention to the government's wrongdoing and dedicated the majority of her time to the cause. Josephine Lukito,

an Assistant Professor at the University of Texas at Austin's School of Journalism and Media conducted a study on how governments use state violence and state-sponsored propaganda to repress social movements and found that “given the persistence of the protests, it appears that states still often resort to violence,” posing a significant challenge for activists (qtd. in Lukito et al., 2022). However, the resilience of protestors shows that people are motivated to prioritize justice even when there are risks involved, and knowing how governments use violence against social movements can help activists plan their actions effectively. Jonathan Pinckney and Miranda Rivers, both program officers with the Program on Nonviolent Action at the United States Institute of Peace review the results of a survey of 550 activists in 27 countries about how the COVID-19 pandemic has impacted different factors of social movements. Although results found that “the public health risk from the pandemic does have a statistically significant negative effect on participation in public protest[s],” new movement methods, such as online activism “appear to impact activists' likelihood of participating in protest” (Pinckney et al., 2020). Activists are creating innovative approaches by shifting to “a virtual workspace, launching online campaigns and engaging in digital organizing” to adapt to the constraints of the pandemic and stay involved in social movements (Pinckney et al., 2020). Individuals who genuinely care about a cause are willing to overcome challenges and continue fighting for justice. They find solutions to problems that get in the way of their goals, proving their commitment to making a difference and inspiring others along the way. Maarten Johannesan van Bezouw, an Assistant Professor at Utrecht University with 18 publications and over 100 citations conducted a study on the types of goals disadvantaged individuals strive to achieve and what motivates them to join a social movement. Individuals often avoid challenging authority because humans are conditioned

to avoid conflict, but “[t]he realization that one is being deprived of important outcomes may increase feelings of entitlement and the likelihood of participating in collective action” (qtd. in van Bezouw et al., 2019). By recognizing the importance of change, activists demonstrate the moral courage to confront systemic injustices. This means confronting powerful opposition and being willing to stand up for what one believes in, even when the decision is not easy or widely accepted. Some individuals may advocate for a cause without a strong sense of purpose, but rather because they feel pressure to conform to societal expectations and fit in with others in their community. Julia Steinberger, a professor of Ecological Economics at the University of Lausanne clarifies that when someone does this by “speak[ing] to another, standing as an individual with integrity and emotion, and makes a claim to that other person’s actions,” it can help them step out of their comfort zone and advocate for a good cause they didn’t initially believe was worthwhile (Steinberger 2022).

In a world where injustice is familiar, our voices and actions matter more than ever, making joining the movement toward positive change necessary by developing moral courage. The proposed solution targets increased moral courage within individuals during social movements. This would be through community-based online support groups. Limitations of this solution would include the digital divide and the inability to build face-to-face connections among participants. Nonetheless, the implications of this solution are strong. Even if this solution limits face-to-face connections, individuals may feel more comfortable speaking out and contributing their ideas on an online platform. People around the world are more likely to participate in social movements with the availability of regular community support. Another

solution that was considered was in-person support groups, but the biggest concerns with this are accessibility and implementation. The exchange of resources and information will be more convenient with the chosen solution in place.

Works Cited

- Lawrence, Jacob. "Confrontation on the Bridge." 1975. Central Kitsap School District, Bremerton, United States of America
- Cui, Ge-Qi, et al. "The Impact of Vertical/Horizontal Individualism and Collectivism on Ethical Consumption." *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 21, Nov. 2022, p. NA. Gale In Context: Science, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A747179557/GPS?u=j043905009&sid=bookmark-GPS&xid=b144d7f7. Accessed 30 Mar. 2024.
- Epstein, Kitty Kelly, and Bernard Stringer. "The Student Strike that Won Ethnic Studies and Black Student College Admissions." *Journal of African American Studies*, vol. 26, no. 4, Dec. 2022, pp. 503+. Gale General OneFile Custom, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A741190307/GPS?u=j043905009&sid=bookmark-GPS&xid=ce971115. Accessed 7 Mar. 2024.
- Gutierrez, Grant M., et al. "The Double Force of Vulnerability: Ethnography and Environmental Justice." *Environment and Society*, vol. 12, no. 1, annual 2021, pp. 66+. Gale In Context: Science, link.gale.com/apps/doc/A707704358/GPS?u=j043905009&sid=bookmark-GPS&xid=43982b85. Accessed 8 Mar. 2024.
- Hansen, Robert. "The Impact of Collective Action and Social Movements on Shaping Society." *The RSnake Show*, 12 Sept. 2023, www.rsnae.com/post/the-impact-of-collective-action-and-social-movements-on-shaping

van Bezouw, Maarten Johannes, and Maja Kutlaca. "What Do We Want? Examining the Motivating Role of Goals in Social Movement Mobilization: Journal of Social and Political Psychology." *What Do We Want? Examining the Motivating Role of Goals in Social Movement Mobilization* | *Journal of Social and Political Psychology*, jspp.psychopen.eu/index.php/jspp/article/view/5121/5121.html. Accessed 25 Mar. 2024.

Zwerman, Gilda, and Michael Schwartz. "How 'good' Social Movements Can Triumph over 'Bad' Ones." *Scientific American*, 20 Feb. 2024, www.scientificamerican.com/article/how-iso-good-rsquo-social-movements-can-triumph-over-iso-bad-rsquo-ones/.